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CONTENT ANALYSIS OF THE SOCIAL REPRESENTATION IN THE NARRATIVES OF CHRONIC PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

In an interdisciplinary approach, we found a possible reading in the analyzed article: “Construction of Meaning in the Narratives of Chronic Patients” and the construction of an analysis based on the expressed content. This construction of speech permeates the entire process of human communication being developed through the relationship of linguistic symbols expressed in speech, that is, in the speech emanated by the subject. Objective: To analyze the content of textual fragments of the article “Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients” by José Roque Junges and Tatiane Bagatini under the framework of Moscovici’s social representation. Methodology: Research with a qualitative approach. For treatment of the material, Bardin’s method of content analysis (1977) was chosen, where he analyzes the content and its inferences in a systematic and objective way, described by Minayo (2000), which organizes it in three stages: analysis, exploration of the material and treatment of the results obtained and interpretation under the framework of Moscovici (1979; 2003; 2009). Results and Discussion: In this study, we used the inferences to compose the content analysis categories, associating them by similarity, generating the categories: diagnosis of the disease, therapeutic and drug treatment become (1) Therapeutic, while body and emotional situation become (2) Social Representation. We emphasize that all respondents are in a moment of physical, emotional, and social fragility resulting from the hospitalization process, which limits full autonomy over health decisions and practices. Final Considerations: We found in the analyzes of the study two distinct processes in the discourse confirming our hypothesis about the attitude influenced by everyday experiences, the study presents objectification and anchoring analyzed based on TRS that demonstrate the role of influence of the daily experience and the transformation of the subjective into objective through the hierarchy of responsibility for their reality.

Keywords: Content Analysis, Discourse, Chronic Patient , Social Representation.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) according to the World Health Organization are classified in a list that includes cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, obstructive respiratory diseases, asthma and neoplasms. In this same list we currently find mental disorders, neurological, oral, bone, joint, auditory diseases, osteoporosis and genetic disorders. (WHO, 2005; THEME FILHA, 2015)

According to Simões et al (2021), the National Health Surveys (INS) allow knowing the profile, distribution and risk factors that affect a given population by analyzing the geographic variables that prevail in each group of diseases. The study evaluated NCDs such as neuropsychiatric disorders (NP), musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) and joint disorders, in addition to chronic renal failure (CRF).

A striking characteristic of CNCDs is the longevity of symptoms, fatigue caused by hospitalizations, long treatments, disabilities, social restrictions generating biological, psychological and social consequences that can be identified in social representations and discourses. (SILVA; CREPALDI; BOUSFIELD, 2021)

Due to the need for qualified listening for these developments, the Ministry of Health (MS) created a public policy called the National Humanization Policy – Humaniza SUS in 2003, among the strategies included qualified listening. This qualified listening, in addition to understanding the processes that the patient experiences, determines possible therapeutic itineraries. (BRASIL 2004; SANTOS, 2019)

In an interdisciplinary approach, we found a possible reading in the analyzed article: “Construction of Meaning in the Narratives of Chronic Patients” and the construction of an analysis based on the expressed content. This construction of speech permeates the entire process of human communication being developed through the relationship of linguistic symbols expressed in speech, that is, in the speech emanated by the subject.

Through this, the question emerges: What is the

social representation that we find in the discourse of chronically ill patients according to Moscovici’s theory of social relations?

Our hypothesis is based on the fact that the construction of the discourse undergoes modification due to the result of socio-economic relations and the construction of the meaning of the disease. The social representation expressed in the speeches will be supported by the attitudes and social influence experienced.

We believe that the prevailing social representation in the discourse is supported by influence relationships and social perception regarding their current health situation and intrapsychic conflicts. generated. The relevance of this study is supported by the belief that the speech undergoes different modifications when interpreted from the perspective of social relations.

GOAL

To analyze the content of fragments of the article “Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients” by José Roque Junges and Tatiane Bagatini under the framework of Moscovici’s social representation.

METHODOLOGY

Research with a qualitative approach to the book “ Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients” by José Roque Junges and Tatiane Bagatini published in the Revista da Associação Médica Brasileira in 2010. For the treatment of the material, Bardin’s method of content analysis (1977) was chosen.) where it analyzes the content and its inferences in a systematic and objective way described by Minayo (2000) who organizes the material in three stages: analysis, exploration of the material and treatment of the obtained results and interpretation. In this study, the framework of Moscovici (1979; 2003; 2009) called Theory of Social Representations (TSR) will be applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The article under analysis contextualizes the

technologies used in the Unified Health System, referencing the democratizing role of access to treatments, argues that technology can cause a distancing effect on quality issues between the professional and the system user.

He states that based on this fact, the Ministry of Health created the Humaniza SUS Program in order to elaborate a specific policy, but we find refutation of this idea in the study by Rios (2009, p.255) who refers to the formulation based on the historical and social context and not merely in terms of user visibility in the system.

Humanization recognizes the field of subjectivities as a fundamental instance for a better understanding of problems and for the search for shared solutions. Participation, autonomy, responsibility and solidarity are values that characterize this way of doing health that results, in the end, in more quality care and better working conditions. Its essence is the alliance of technical and technological competence with ethical and relational competence .

The griffin above affirms the importance of subjectivity, but combined with technical and technological competence. We find in technical competence the issue of qualified listening, that is, attentive listening with the purpose of welcoming the user and bonding. (COELHO; JORGE, 2009) The study authors describe the use of a qualitative approach through a semi-structured questionnaire, the study sample 17 participants between 25 and 65 years old hospitalized in a public hospital unit in the metropolitan region of Porto Alegre. The study does not describe within the initial sample how many respondents are in these characteristics, it states the use of only 6 interviews for analysis. It is important to emphasize that the study was evaluated by the Ethics Committee of UNISINOS with Resolution nº 053/2004.

The sample of the material analyzed is predominantly female, which demonstrates a fragility in the analyzes as it makes it impossible to verify the existence of a pattern of discourse between groups and genders.

In the results and discussion, we found the organization of the speech in the utterance, being composed of categories such as: diagnosis of the disease, therapeutic treatment, body, medicine, emotional situation, being analyzed in the light of the Bakhtinian Theory.

In this study, we will use the identified inferences to compose categories for content analysis through similarity: “disease diagnosis, therapeutic and drug treatment” become (1) Therapeutics, while “body and emotional situation” become (2) Social Representation.

Below is an expository table with the categories and textual fragments for analysis according to Moscovici’s theory of social representation.

CHART 1: ORGANIZATION OF CATEGORIES AND TEXTUAL FRAGMENTS. MOGI DAS CRUZES, 2023.

Therapy	<p>“Ah, sometimes I get really sad because I think I went to eat those things I couldn’t. Now it’s late. Now you have to live your life” (Textual fragment 1)</p> <p>“No, because this is something that runs in the family, because the old people had it, my mother, my father and all the brothers. Some have already died” (Textual fragment 2)</p> <p>“Ah, I think that if I do my treatment correctly, eat what the doctor says, then there will be salvation. If I do everything wrong, I will never recover” (Textual fragment 3)</p> <p>“Look, I think it’s the psychologist. We can vent, talk a lot, I cry, I talk. It’s not just giving an injection or giving a sleeping pill. I think it’s better to sit down and talk than give medicine” (Textual fragment 4)</p>
Social Representation	<p>(1) I found out because of high blood pressure (a) when I was pregnant - I left the hospital - very heavy body, I walked with that weight - always heavy belly, always stuffed (b) I went to the maternity ward - I had swollen feet and a hundred or so kilos, it was all liquid in the body. (2) “I went for an exam, an ultrasound, I had to undergo hemodialysis” - “I was all swollen, everything was liquid” - “I felt tired, heavy” (c) “When I went to deliver the child, it looked like I was going to gain more than a baby” (Textual fragment 5)</p>

Source: JUNGES, J. R.; BAGATINI, T.. Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients. *Journal of the Brazilian Medical Association*, v. 56, n.2, p. 179-185)

We can verify in the therapeutic category in the textual fragment (1) and (3) the reference to situations related to the act or dietary restriction reflects a social issue, eating is a social and gregarious act and is subject to interference from the place where the individual is inserted.

Fragment 1: “ Ah, sometimes I get really sad because I think I went to eat those things I couldn't . Now it's late. Now you have to take life ”. (GRIFFIN OUR)

Fragment 3 : “Ah, I think that if I do my treatment correctly, eat what the doctor says , then there will be salvation. If I get it all wrong, I'll never recover.” (GRIFFIN OUR)

Applying the Theory of Social Representation, we find the statement in the studies of Samuel and Polli (2020) :

[...] social representations can be understood as the re-presentation of everyday phenomena. This re-presentation occurs when people collectively think, position themselves, express themselves and share thoughts and reproduce social representations. To get to know the world and make it more controllable and close, people create social representations. That is, the individual actively participates in the construction of social thought, explaining and giving meaning to everyday facts [...]

We found in fragments (2) and (4) the discourse of the need to recognize family situations that interfere in the current dynamics of the interviewee's life, but Mosconici (1979) starts from the belief that there is no cut between the external universe and the individual (group) and yes, of its interrelationship between the subject and the other subject. Thus, the author refers to the reciprocal influence of the social structure and that of the subject.

Fragment 2: No, because this is something that runs in the family, because the old people had it, my mother, my father and all the brothers. Some have already died

Fragment 4 : “ Look, I think it's the psychologist. We can vent, talk a lot, I cry, I talk. It's not just giving an injection or giving a sleeping pill. I think it's better to sit and talk than to give medicine”

In the Social Representation category, we can verify the discourse associated with the interviewee's discovery of the need for hemodialysis treatment:

Fragment 5: (1) I found out because of high blood pressure (a) when I was pregnant - I left the hospital - very heavy body, I walked with that weight - belly always heavy, always stuffed (b) I went to be given birth at the maternity ward - I had swollen feet and a hundred and something kilos, it was all liquid in the body. (2) “I went for an exam, an ultrasound, I had to undergo hemodialysis” - “I was all swollen, everything was liquid” - “I felt tired, heavy” (c) “When I went to deliver the child, it looked like I was going to gain more than a baby”

It is noteworthy that some speech characteristics only describe characteristics of the end of the third gestational trimester. The report describes pregnancy complications: (1) I found out because of high blood pressure (a) when I was pregnant - I left the hospital - very heavy body, I walked with that weight - belly always heavy, always stuffed (b) I went to gain weight in the maternity ward - I was with swollen feet and three hundred pounds, it was all liquid in her body.

Already in the part: (1) I found out because of high blood pressure (a) when I was pregnant, we can reflect different situations: I was having prenatal care so I was considered high risk? If so, the interlocutor could have already received the guidelines, requiring adherence to treatment.

Gomes, Mendonça and Pontes (2002, p.1210) state:

“How would this event be expressed and how would it be possible to understand it? The idea of text, as a written fixation

of discourse, allows the rehabilitation of theories of discourse in their temporal updating, contemplating the meaning of the message, which persists and must be understood.”

The article by Junges and Bagatini (2010) reports that the interviewed group presents a predominance of morbidities: diabetes mellitus (DM), systemic arterial hypertension (SAH), chronic renal failure (CRF) and depression. It is worth mentioning that all interviewees are in a moment of physical, emotional and social fragility, the hospitalization process is presented in a coercive way, that is, without full autonomy of decision about their health, these situations and speeches emanated suffer this isolation bias Social.

According to the Theory of Social Representations (SRT), we identified in the composition of the speeches the presence of intrapsychic and interpersonal conflicts, latent and “covered” attitudes towards the restrictions that the disease emanates, the presence of information about their health-disease process with preponderance the hierarchization and lack of autonomy of decisions. (SANTOS, 1994)

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

We found in the analysis of the study two processes in the speech confirming our hypothesis about the attitude influenced by everyday experiences. The study presents objectification and anchoring described in TRS. Objectification is related to the formulation of ideas based on the categorization of feelings contained in the speeches, such as ordering and classifying actions, turning something subjective into real. The anchoring present in the speeches is observed in the discourse of the hierarchy of values and meanings resulting from the progressive process of the disease.

It is important to contextualize that in some speeches we find the statement “improvement when talking” with a psychologist, which should not be identified by the interviewee because it generates the false idea that qualified listening occurs only by this professional and not by a

multidisciplinary team.

REFERENCES

BARDIN, L. Content analysis. Lisbon: Editora Edições 70, 1977.

BRAZIL. Ministry of Health. Humaniza SUS. National Humanization Policy. Humanization as a guiding principle of care practices in all instances of the SUS. Brasília (DF): Ministry of Health; 2004.

COELHO, MO; JORGE, MSB. Technology of relationships as a device for humanized care in primary health care from the perspective of access, acceptance and bonding. *Ciência & Saúde Coletiva*, v. 14, p. 1523–1531, Sept. 2009. Accessed on: 07/16/2023. Available at: <https://www.scielo.br/j/csc/a/F8cMBSY8RtNZw3349gRrLqR/>

GOMES, R.; MENDONÇA, EA; PONTES, ML. Social representations and the experience of the disease. *Public Health Notebooks*, v. 18, no. 5, p. 1207–1214, Sept. 2002. Accessed on: 07/16/2023. Available at: <https://www.scielo.br/j/csp/a/bmK7md56D7MSpjYkMYs3SLd/>

JUNGES, J, R.; BAGATINI, T.. Construction of meaning in the narratives of chronically ill patients. *Journal of the Brazilian Medical Association*, v. 56, n.2, p. 179-185) Accessed on: 07/16/2023. Available at: <https://www.scielo.br/j/ramb/a/PTLcBSJQz8MhPh9psynbtgS/>

MINAYO, MCS The challenge of knowledge, qualitative health research. 7th Edition, São Paulo-Rio de Janeiro. Hucitec-Abrasco, 2000.

MOSCOVICI, S. Les representations sociales: a lost concept. Originally published in: *El psicoanálisis, su imagen y su publico*. Buenos Aires: Huemul, 1979. (Digitized).

_____. The power of ideas. In: *Social Representations: Investigations in Social Psychology*. Edited in English by Gerard Duveen; Translated from English by Pedrinho A. Guareschi. Petrópolis, RJ: Voices, 2003.

- _____. Social representations: investigations in social psychology. 6. ed. Petrópolis, RJ: Voices, 2009.
- RIOS, IC. Humanization: the essence of technical and ethical action in health practices. *Brazilian Journal of Medical Education* , v. 33, no. 2, p. 253–261, Apr. 2009. Accessed on: 07/10/2023. Available at: <https://www.scielo.br/j/rbem/a/LwsQggyXBqqf8tW6nLd9N6v/>
- SAMUEL, Ligia Ziegler; POLLI, Gislei Mocelin. Social representations and eating disorders: systematic review. *Bol. - Acad. Paul. Psychol.* , São Paulo , v. 40, no. 98, p. 91-99, Jun. 2020 . Available at http://pepsic.bvsalud.org/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1415-711X202000100010&lng=pt&nrm=iso . Hits on 12 Jul. 2023.
- SANTOS, AB Qualified listening as a tool for the humanization of mental health care in Primary Care. *APS IN REVIEW* , [S. l.] , v. 1, no. 2, p. 170–179, 2019. DOI: 10.14295/aps.v1i2.23. Available at: <https://apsemrevista.org/aps/article/view/23> . Accessed on: 12 Jul. 2023.
- SANTOS, Maria de Fatima de Souza. Social representation and the individual-society relationship. *Psychological themes.* , Ribeirão Preto , v. 2, no. 3, p. 133-142, Dec. 1994. Available at http://pepsic.bvsalud.org/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1413-389X1994000300013&lng=pt&nrm=iso . Hits on 16 Jul. 2023.
- SILVA, Jean Paulo da; CREPALDI, Maria Aparecida; BOUSFIELD, Andréa Barbará da Silva. Social representations and chronic diseases in the family context: integrative review. *Rev. Psicol. Health* , Campo Grande , v. 13, no. 2, p. 125-140, Jun. 2021 . Available at <http://pepsic.bvsalud.org/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S2177-093X2021000200010&lng=pt&nrm=iso>. Hits on 12 Jul. 2023. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20435/pssa.v13i2.964> .
- SIMÕES, taynãna César et al. Prevalence of chronic diseases and access to health services in Brazil: evidence from three household surveys. *Ciência & Saúde Coletiva* [online]. v. 26, no. 09 [Accessed 12 July 2023] , pp. 3991-4006. Available at: <<https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232021269.02982021>>. ISSN 1678-4561. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1413-81232021269.02982021> .
- THEME FILHA, MM el al... Prevalence of non-transmissible chronic diseases and association with self-rated health: National Health Survey, 2013. *Revista Brasileira de Epidemiologia*, v. 18, p.83-96, Dec.2015. Accessed on: 07/17/2023. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-5497201500060008>
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION. (2005) . Preventing chronic diseases : a vital investment : WHO global report. World Health Organization. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/43314>